

Investigation of Socially Intelligible Young People Introduction to the Labour Market

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ABSTRACT

Youth unemployment is a problem relevant to the whole world, and Lithuania is not different. Although in recent years, due to the efforts of various government and non-government organizations, youth unemployment has a tendency to decrease, however, it has been higher than the total unemployment rate in the country during the whole Lithuania's independence. The social costs of youth unemployment are very high. Youth unemployment today is a growing social problem tomorrow. The behaviour of young people in the labour market depends on many social, economic, demographic and other closely related factors. Youth unemployment, as a socio-economic phenomenon, is a particularly disadvantageous result of the interaction of these factors. Article analyses youth unemployment and respondents' opinion about socially intelligible young people's introduction to the labour market.

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KEYWORDS: *young people, labour market, youth employment, youth employment opportunities*

1. INTRODUCTION

Each youth generation has characteristics that distinguish it from the parents' generation or other generations by developing its own characteristic expression forms that depend on the economic, social and political peculiarities of the life of that time. In fact, it is a special part of the society, that has its own specific problems, properties, interests which require the attention of the state and other public institutions. The youth uniqueness is related to the period of human life, when it is integrating into society, is widened and becomes independent, attempts to get established in the labour market, begins creating a family and life well-being.

2. YOUTH EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES IN LITHUANIA

Youth unemployment is the most important social problem of youth. When employing young people, employers take into account not only their acquired education but also other qualities such as: the ability to communicate, organize, create and work in a team. In this situation, employer's and young person's attitude towards these abilities are distinguished, as young people mostly think that they have mastered them perfectly during studies, and most employers look the other way round and are convinced that science is based on theoretical knowledge without providing the young people with the necessary practical skills. It is widely accepted that most skills are acquired only through work

and real-world situations. Moreover, young people often miss out on the fact that they are well experienced with information technology, which is widespread in this generation. In addition, the information technology and services sector are integral parts and not mentioning the seemingly unimportant fact may have a lot to do with. This is a risky step for the employer to take on a such worker, especially during the crisis period, as the majority of service companies in Lithuania were forced to reduce their staff, that in the fairy tale says that the labour exchange does not have to find a job for people who have acquired various qualifications and education, thus leaving young people to the country. Therefore, the problem is that young people may find themselves in a social isolation for a long time not finding a job. Different authors have interpreted the concept of social exclusion in different times in different countries (Littlewood and Herkommer, 1999; Saith 2001, Biggin, 2004). According to French investigator Paugam (1996) "sociologists must first acknowledge the impossibility of formulating comprehensive definitions of poverty and social exclusion. These concepts are relative and diverse, depending on the time and circumstances." Some people understand the concept of social exclusion from the individual's identity, others value it as a particular state or situation of an individual (Zaleskienė, 1998); One accepts social exclusion as a dynamic process of an individual's life

(others - as a consequence of the development of society, which is fixed in a social organization and determined by it. In other words, "social exclusion is an inalienable departure from economic and social values."

According to Eurostat, in the European Union (EU) 2016 117.5 million people, or 23.4% of the EU population were at risk of poverty or social exclusion. This means that they lived in households with at least one of the following conditions: the risk of poverty after social benefits (income poverty), severe material deprivation or very low employment. 2009-2012 the percentage of people in the EU who were at risk of poverty or social exclusion increased by 25%, then gradually decreased and in 2016 it was 23.4%, only by 0.1% exceeding the lowest point of 2009.

3. INTEGRATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE INTO THE LABOUR MARKET

On January 1st, 2018, there were 24,1 thousand registered 16 - 29 year old young people, and that is less by 0,3 thousand than a year ago (as of January 1st, 2017 there were 24.4 thousand). January 1st, 2018, 16 - 29 years olds accounted for 15.8 percent of all the unemployed (16.1% on January 1st, 2017). Therefore, in order to reduce youth unemployment, it is important to promote the young unemployed integration into the labour market. The integration is the parts integration of into a whole body, restoration, renewal. The integration can be characterised as the natural right of every individual to fully participate in public life (Gudžinskienė, Jurgutiene, 2010). The Lithuanian Labour Exchange also contributes to the young people integration into the labour market, which provides various services and tools for employment. Various measures are used to integrate young unemployed into the labour market, and they can be grouped into two groups. The first group includes permanent or fixed-term employment, while the second group includes active labour market measures that include supported employment (i.e. acquisition of work skills, public works), vocational training, job rotation, job creation. Research carried out by Kriščiūnienė (2011) has confirmed that people seeking to integrate into the labour market are increasingly interested in the possibility of temporarily employing via employment agency services. However, De Cuyper, de Jong, De Witte, Isaksson, Rigotti, & Schalk (2008) emphasized that temporary employment is not an appropriate means of integrating into the labour market, since in the long run such form of employment may adversely affect person's further employment opportunities. Most scientific sources highlight the main problems and obstacles that prevent young people from gaining a foothold in the labour market. (Karamessini, 2010; Semboja, 2007) highlighting the main youth employment opportunities, emphasizes the importance of encouraging young people's interest in vocational education and training institutions, as employers expect young people to receive practical, rather than theoretical, skills. Researchers (Hannan et al., 1996) also state that the problem of youth employment is contributing to the recession of the state itself, as the economic crisis has led many employers to endure long-term employees, while young people remain underestimated due to lack of experience and shortage of seniority. However, the next question is how young people can gain experience if no one wants to hire them. Studies by the aforementioned authors show that in the European Union countries, structural unemployment is also prevalent in Lithuania, which in the theoretical definition is described as labour

demand mismatch with labour supply. Therefore, there are problems with the young people employment opportunities. It can be argued that it is precisely the discrepancy between labour supply and the fact that many young people are currently unemployed and unable to establish themselves in the market. Most of them chose not specially tailored specialties or just picked up the most in demand, whose specialists' jobs in Lithuania have long been filled. The causes of youth unemployment may be as diverse as the social factors of the country, as well as the country's economic context - the economic crisis in Lithuania. Other possibilities that could lead to more favourable youth employment conditions: interaction between education and employment institutions (Beresnevičiūtė, Poviliūnas, 2007), opportunities for reconciliation of studies and work, as well as wage regulation measures motivating young specialists to look for work according to their specialty.

Therefore, in order to reduce youth unemployment, it is important to promote the integration of young unemployed into labour market. Integration is the integration of parts into a whole, restoration, renewal. Integration can be characterized as the natural right of every individual to participate fully in public life (Gudžinskienė, Jurgutiene, 2010: 18). The Lithuanian Labour Exchange also contributes to the integration of young people into the labour market, which provides various services and tools for employment. Various measures are used to integrate young unemployed into the labour market, and they can be grouped into two groups. The second group includes active labour market measures, that include supported employment (i.e., work skills acquisition, public works), vocational training, job rotation, job creation. The research conducted by A. Kriščiūnienė (2011) has confirmed that people seeking to integrate into the labour market are increasingly interested in the possibility of temporarily employing employment agency services. However, D. Jong and R. Witte (2008) emphasized that temporary employment is not an appropriate means of integrating into the labour market, since in the long run such a form of employment may adversely affect further employment opportunities for a person. Most scientific literature highlights the main problems and obstacles that prevent young people from gaining a foothold in the labour market. (Karamessini, 2010; Semboja, 2007; Ryan, 1999), highlighting the main youth employment opportunities, emphasizes the importance of encouraging young people's interest in vocational education and training institutions, as employers expect young people to receive practical, rather than theoretical, skills. Researchers (Hannan et al., 1996) also state that the problem of youth employment is contributing to the recession of the state itself, as the economic crisis has led many employers to endure long-term employees, while young people remain underestimated due to experience and shortage of seniority. However, the next question is how young people can gain experience if no one wants to hire them. Studies by the aforementioned authors show that in the countries of the European Union, structural unemployment is also prevalent in Lithuania, which in the theoretical definition is described as labour demand mismatch with labour supply. Therefore, there are problems with the employment opportunities of young people. It can be argued that it is precisely the discrepancy between labour supply and the fact that many young people are currently unemployed and unable to establish themselves in the market. Most of them chose not specially tailored specialties

or just picked up the most in demand, whose specialists' jobs in Lithuania have long been filled. The causes of youth unemployment may be as diverse as the social factors of the country, as well as the country's economic context - the economic crisis in Lithuania. Other possibilities that could lead to more favourable youth employment conditions: interaction between education and employment institutions (Beresnevičiūtė, Poviliūnas, 2007), opportunities for reconciliation of studies and work, as well as wage regulation measures motivating young specialists to look for work accordingly to their specialty. Integrating of young people into the labour market is affected by a wide range of factors: the development of services and production, education, work motivation, health, family livelihood and living standards. Factors can be grouped according to various criteria. Factors influencing the processes of integration of young people into the labour market can be grouped into exogenous (external) and endogenous (internal). Exogenous - factors beyond the control of the individual, which he cannot directly regulate. They include socioeconomic, social, demographic, geographic and political factors that both have a positive and negative impact on the employment rate of young people. Youth activism and employment rates are raising the ability of young workers and professionals to adapt to the rapidly changing labour market conditions. However, nevertheless, most employers consider that young workers often lack professional qualifications, lacking the necessary experience. Looking at the social side and discussing social factors, we can observe that social life is very diverse and complex. The family is the first institute that nurtures and "launches" a young man into a distant life. Parents are very important people, shaping a young personality, they transmit social values, teach morals and other things important to the person. Thus, parents are, nevertheless, greatly influenced by their ability to pursue higher education in terms of their situation. The more difficult social situation a family is in, the more difficulties a young person faces trying to integrate into society and the labour market. The desire of the youth to learn, to receive certain knowledge, to understand the importance of science, to achieve the material well-being, is conditioned by the career ladder. The number of young people willing to study is increasing every year. Everyone can choose a high school or a different school according to their needs, desires and opportunities.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE SOCIALLY VULNERABLE YOUNG PEOPLE INTEGRATION INTO THE LABOUR MARKET

Investigation methodology. The questionnaire contained 20 questions aimed at elucidating the respondents' opinion on the possibilities of integration of young people into the labour market and current problems. The study involved 132 respondents.

Detailed estimates of these people are presented graphically.

Figure 1. Respondents distribution by gender

During the survey, the aim was to find out the gender of the respondents. The results showed that the questionnaire was mostly answered by women

Figure 2. Respondents distribution by age

More than half of respondents who participated in the survey aged 18 to 24 years. Also, many respondents were between 25 and 30 years old.

Half of respondents who participated in the survey, the place of residence is a city. There are also a number of respondents from a village or town / settlement.

More than half of respondents have secondary education. Respondents with higher or vocational education are equally distributed.

41.2 percent are students, 25.9% are only employed persons, 22.4% are working students and 9.4% are unemployed.

Most of the respondents did not experience employer discrimination because of their age, but there were also respondents who were partially experienced and who have experienced discrimination due to their age.

The most common reason for non-employment was the following: they are not satisfied with wages, lack of work experience, and one of the main reasons for this is due to the additional employer requirements. It is precisely this reason that seems to be the most important for respondents, which makes it difficult for young people to find a job.

The data presented show that young people lack the most basic theoretical knowledge at the beginning of their professional activity, and most of them lack practical knowledge.

Figure 3. Have you ever experienced employers discrimination due to your age?

Less than half of respondents agree that older people have more job opportunities. Also 26 percent respondents disagree with this opinion and 24% fully agree that older people have more employment opportunities.

33 percent respondents have job experience from 1 to 4 years, 32% respondents have up to a year work experience and there were such respondents who do not have a seniority.

One third of the respondents do not have a permanent job for 6-12 months, 28.2% permanent job does not have 24 months or more and 21.2 percent of respondents did not answer this question.

One third of respondents answered that they intend to work within a month. Slightly fewer respondents plan to work within 2-3 months and 15% plans to find work in half a year.

Figure 4. Does your speciality meet the needs of the labour market

Almost half of the respondents answered that their acquired speciality or qualification meets the needs of the labour market. One third of the respondents do not have an opinion on this issue.

Figure 5. What is the cause non-compliance with the needs of the labour market?

The most common reason for the lack of compliance with the needs of the labour market was the lack of willingness to recruit new specialists. One third of them say there are too many specialists.

Respondents have indicated that wages and salaries are the most important choices in their work, and it is equally important to have access to work and do the work.

Almost half of the respondents said that the most youth employment was influenced by the acquired education and specialty. Also, work experience and skills are influenced by employment as well as by personal characteristics such as: diligence, communication, responsibility, etc., and the least influences are the labour exchange and its services

Almost all respondents said that young people are themselves responsible for their employment. The average responsibility is for parents and state.

According to the respondents, a young person is very sensitive to paid wages before getting to work, and also the career opportunities offered are relevant, and it is not relevant for young people to work for their favourite and interesting job.

Almost half of the respondents said they will relocate abroad if they won't be able to find a job. One third of the respondents do not know whether they will stay or will leave.

CONCLUSIONS

According to the questionnaire data, the current situation of young people integration into the labour market and the prevailing problems are:

Target market - women - students aged 18 to 24 who live in the city, their education is secondary, not graduated, and their length of service is from 1 to 4 years.

When responding to the question "For how long you don't have a permanent job?" most chose the answer between 6-12 months. They expect to start working in one month. The respondents believe that their unemployment is caused by: insufficient work experience, not big enough wages, and one more reason is high employers' demands.

According to the question "What do you need to get a job faster?" one third of the respondents said that there was a need to improve their qualifications or re-qualify, as well as an insufficient assessment of professional skills when choosing a job.

More than half of the respondents said that the most they lack practical training from the beginning of their professional life, and also a significant lack of personal skills. The specialty and qualification acquired by the respondents correspond to the needs of the labour market. They also believe that the reason for not meeting the needs of the labour market is the reluctance to receive young specialists. The respondents take salary into account when choosing a job, and that the work corresponds to the qualification.

The young people employment is most influenced by the acquired education and vocational training, work experience and skills, while the least influenced by the labour exchange and its services. Also, when choosing a job, salaries and career opportunities are most important to young people, but it is less important relevant for young people to work their favourite and interesting jobs. The survey showed that if respondents won't find a job in the near future, they intend to go abroad.

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